

iFR: A NEW FRAMEWORK FOR REAL-TIME FACE RECOGNITION WITH MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

Biometric authentication is widely used nowadays by many developers and business sector. This includes the mobile phone industries which implement face identification to unlock the mobile phones and companies that use this technology to tighten their security. Face identification is also used in taking the attendance. However, this technology appears to have a hole where people can easily spoof it such as by using photo attack attempt. In addition, this technology needs to be intelligent and fast enough to process and decide. In this study, we are using eye blink detection method to avoid the attempt of spoofing and deep learning which is a sub-category of machine learning to improve the system to be intelligent and fast. Generally, we are trying to make a system which is not hardware dependable as the hardware tends to change from time to time. Thus, in this study, we are focusing in studying the algorithms to develop the system. We use deep learning approach, Tensorflow framework, FaceNet and Multi-task Convolutional Neural Networks (MTCNN) as part of the elements in the system. At the end of our study, we hope that this research work and upcoming system can be used in real environment, spoofing problem can be eliminated and the system will be intelligent and fast enough to decide and work by itself without human intervention.

1 INTRODUCTION

This research study is about developing an intelligent face recognition system that can eliminate spoofing by using eye blink detection and

identify a person by using deep learning in Tensorflow framework. The objectives of this research are first to study about deep learning and Tensorflow framework, thus implement deep learning by using Tensorflow framework in recognizing a face. Second, to study a method to avoid spoofing and create a face recognition system that can eliminate spoofing such as photo attack and third, to make a smarter system by using machine learning approach where it can learn to do things by itself by just giving it instructions. In this study, we are using the existing methods which are deep learning and Tensorflow framework in identifying a face. This implementation will also be tested on covered face to determine whether it can identify a face that may partially covered with something.

Nowadays, people are exposed to the face authentication and that leads to spoofing like photo attack. This will make the system become insecure. From logical thinking, a real person will blink and a static image will not blink. In average, a person blinks 15-20 times per minute which is a person blinks every four seconds. Based on this, to eliminate spoofing, eye blink detection is implemented in the system. This research work deals with videos as the processing input. However, static images will also be used but only in testing for spoofing using photo attack.

At the end of this research study, the system is believed to be able to have a short processing time, eliminate spoofing and be more accurate in identifying a face.

2 PROPOSED WORK

In this research study, deep learning will be used in identifying faces. The deep learning approach is implemented using Tensorflow framework in creating deep learning models. This system starts with face detection, eye blink detection followed by face recognition and displaying result.

A. Face detection

In every face recognition system, it will start with face detection. Like in this study, the face is first need to be detected before cropping the face region. To detect a face, we use Haar cascade classifier from OpenCV [1]. The accuracy of face detected will be controlled using scaleFactor variables. Low scaleFactor will have less accurate face detection and vice versa. Figure below shows the steps for face detection by using OpenCV.

Figure 1 Steps in Face Detection using OpenCV

B. Eye blink detection

Eye blink detection will take place before the system perform the recognizing process. This system is designed to eliminate spoofing (i.e. photo attack) by using eye blink detection. We detect eye blink with OpenCV, Python and dlib [2]. Figure below shows the steps of eye blink detection.

Figure 2 Steps in Eye Blink Detection using OpenCV, Python and dlib

C. Face Recognition

In this research study, deep learning is used for identifying a face by using Tensorflow. Tensorflow is created by Google as an open source library that is used to implement deep learning systems. In this environment, we use FaceNet [3] to build the face recognition network. By using FaceNet model, the triplet loss is calculated for training. Triplet loss is about minimizing the distance between an anchor and a positive which both have the same identity and maximizing the distance between an anchor and a negative which both have different identity. The model used is a pre-trained model

In addition, we use a large number of images as our training data. At the beginning, we use the available dataset as our training data. CASIA Face Image Database Version 5.0 has 2500 color facial images of 500 subjects. The dataset has typical variations which include illumination, pose, expression, eye-glasses and imaging distance [4]. Throughout this research study, we are gathering our own dataset with different variations.

Figure 3 Example of Face Images in CASIA-FaceV5

The faces of training images are aligned by using Multi-task Convolutional Neural Networks (MTCNN). This method is introduced by Zhang [5] and it is used to identify, detect and align the faces by making eyes and bottom lip appear in the same location on each image.

References

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Figure 4 iFR Cross Functional Flowchart